

Being a 21st Century English Teacher

Siendo un profesor de inglés en el siglo 21

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ABSTRACT

The main objective in this article is to inform any teacher of the needs, skills and abilities that can help students and teachers to develop depending on each class and study group in charge. Through this article, it will demonstrate how the techniques and tools applicable in the classes can be adapted to the current situation of the year 2020; whether they are developed virtually or when we return to the physical classrooms. The questions to be developed are shown next to the problem. Questions that; must be answered to have a clearer idea of what we want to demonstrate in the process of teaching and learning English and its techniques, teacher's roles and how to incorporate these tools and techniques in the classes of English as a foreign language; to make this an optimal experience for the English teachers and of course the students who make set goals to obtain the best results at the end of each cycle. Without forgetting that this article aims to inform all those who are teachers and those who are looking to develop new ways of carrying out higher education that in this 21st century technology is present in all our environments. We must continue to change and innovate techniques and tools without forgetting, of course, the use mainly of information

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and communication technologies that are increasingly used in the teaching and learning process to develop in university students a second language that helps them to seek more and better horizons.

Keywords: *21st century skills, EFL classroom, TICs, learning, teaching.*

RESUMEN

El principal objetivo en este artículo es dar a conocer a cualquier docente las necesidades, habilidades y destrezas que podemos hacer que los estudiante y maestros desarrollen dependiendo de cada clase y grupo de estudio a cargo. Demostrando, a través de este artículo cómo acoplarse con la situación actual de este año 2020 las técnicas y herramientas aplicables en nuestras clases; sean estas de forma virtual cómo se desarrollan en la actualidad o cuando ya se vuelva a las aulas físicas. Pasando por la problemática, junto a este se muestran las preguntas a desarrollar. Preguntas que; deben ser respondidas para tener una idea más clara de lo que se quiere demostrar en el proceso de enseñanza aprendizaje del inglés y sus técnicas, roles del profesor y cómo incorporar estas herramientas y técnicas en las clases de inglés como lengua extranjera; para hacer de esta una experiencia óptima para los profesores de inglés y por supuesto los estudiantes que son quienes nos hacen fijarnos metas para poder obtener el mejor de los resultados al final de cada ciclo. Sin olvidar que este artículo tiene el afán de informar a todo aquel que es maestro y a quienes buscan como desarrollar nuevas formas de llevar a cabo la enseñanza superior que en este siglo 21 la tecnología está presente en todos los entornos. Se debe seguir cambiando e innovando las técnicas y herramientas sin olvidar por supuesto el empleo principalmente de las tecnologías de la información y comunicación que se emplean cada vez más en el proceso de enseñanza aprendizaje para desarrollar en los estudiantes universitarios una segunda lengua que les ayude a buscar más y mejores horizontes.

Palabras clave: *aprendizaje, aula de EFL, enseñanza, habilidades del siglo XXI, TICs.*

INTRODUCTION

Recent technological advances have affected many areas of our lives, including the way of communication, collaborate, learn, and, of course, teach. Those advances necessitate an expansion of the vocabulary, producing definitions such as digital natives, digital

immigrants, and the 21st-century teacher. The 21st-century world is characterized by the emergence of the second wave of globalization. If the first wave was triggered by industrial technologies, the second by ICT. The invention of ICT has aborted some scientists' and artists' predictions on the critical roles of flying cars in anticipating of the increasing needs of face-to-face. Now, ICT has made distant face-to-face communication possible. Consequently, extremely overcrowded traffic may not be the case for the business today. The development of ICT however, has led teachers to take new perspectives in their teaching. They are now posed to the more challenging world which requires that they be literate in ICT and skilful in using ICT-based resources and facilities in their teaching. The importance of students' personality quality positive character and good behaviour is compulsory for the success of English teacher education. This quality will serve as the basis for the development of necessary soft skill for successful 21st century English teachers without which the achievement will turn to be counterproductive assets for our national development. (Bellanca, 2010)

For the very reason, religiosity needs to be positioned in the centre of this enterprise. With the aforementioned consideration, the 21st century English teacher education should be well-placed between the importance of ICT literacy and the quality of students' religiosity. Being a 21st century English teachers means develop excellent English communicative competence; while religiosity will help them develop quality soft skills. In other words, religiosity is like the wheeling steer. Education will only result in smart but corrupt individuals. The end of this way of doing education will be as what is stated by Dr Pasha: "*Education without character is at best a waste and at worst quite possibly a pretty dangerous thing.*" (Suherdi, 2012)

Along with new development in science and technology, being a 21st century English has gained more prestige and new demands in its teaching and research. 21st English teacher education should now be put in a new perspective. English teacher education should be designed to inculcate religiosity as the most empowering local identity as well as the global world related competences. English teachers in this century should be aware that they should successfully lead their students to master high standard of English so that they will be able to make the best use of ICT to maximize their contribution to the welfare, peace, and prosperity of mankind and other creatures throughout the universe. In the meantime, global

life also poses new challenges that might lead students to destruction. Some related data shows that while the number of people internet users is among the biggest in the world, the use is far from constructive purposes. That's why religiosity, local wisdom, good character and positive attitude should be an integral part of the English teacher education curricula. (TRILLING & FADEL, 2009) P21 or Partnership for the 21st Century Skills will have used as the main references in this in this research paper. (Meek, 2010)

To participate effectively in the increasingly complex societies and a globalized economy that characterize today's world, students need to think critically, communicate effectively, collaborate with diverse peers, solve complex problems, adopt a global mindset, and engage with information and communications technologies, to name but just a few requirements. There is, however, an agreement that there is a deep gap between the skills that students learn in school and those they need in life and work in the knowledge-based society, and that the current English language curriculum is no longer sufficient to prepare students for life and work in today's changing world of technology (M. Alemi, 2010). (Richards, 2006) states that, as a result of the studies that analysed the work required by the labour market in the 21st century to determine the skills required for EFL students, the present English language programs in EFL contexts lack the necessary 21st-century skills and that the EFL students are provided with traditional skills that do not address their higher thinking skills. This research attempts to fill an academic gap by looking into 21st-century skills and how these skills can be integrated into English language learning, especially in EFL settings. To the researcher's knowledge, this process of integration is understudied and the need for more insights is essential for effective English language learning practices.

METHODOLOGY

To collect data for the current research, the researcher used the descriptive approach. The descriptive approach is mainly used to give an account of 21st century skills and to determine the skills that should be integrated with English language learning. The research is mainly qualitative. Also, the researcher used the deductive approach to reach conclusion based on the data collected from the literature of 21st century skills and English language learning. To collect data for this paper, the researcher used the accredited academic data bases such as ERIC, the relevant journal articles, the dissertations, and published books.

This paper attempts to answer the following questions that can reflect about being a 21st English teacher:

1. What are the 21th Century Skills in the EFL classroom?
2. What are the characteristics of The EFL classroom in the 21st century?
3. How to incorporate 21st century skills into the EFL classroom?

RESULTS

What are the 21th Century Skills in the EFL classroom?

Dimensions of 21st Century Learning skills:

Technological Literacy, Visual and Information Literacy Cultural Literacy and Global Awareness	Inventive Thinking
Digital Age Literacy	Higher-Order Thinking and Sound Reasoning
Basic, Scientific and	Managing Complexity and Self-Direction
	Curiosity, Creativity and Risk-Taking
	Adaptability

Effective Communication	High Productivity
Teaming, Collaboration and Interpersonal Skills	Prioritizing, Planning and Managing for Results
Person, Social and Civic Responsibility	Effective Use of Real-World Tools
Interactive Communication	Ability to Produce Relevant and High-Quality Products

21st Century Skills According to ATC21s (Marilyn Binkley, 2012)

<i>Broad Competencies</i>	<i>Ways of Thinking</i>	<i>Ways of Working</i>	<i>Tools for Working</i>	<i>Living in the World</i>
Universal Skills	Creativity and Innovation, Critical thinking, Problem Solving, Decision Making, learning to learn, Metacognition	Communication, Collaboration and Teamwork	Information Literacy, Research of sources, ICT literacy	Local and Global Citizenship, Life and Career, Personal and Social Responsibility, Cultural Awareness and Competence

The 7 Roles of a Teacher in the 21st Century:

- Think about the kind of lesson as teacher normally teach:
- Which roles are they and you often involved?
- Are there any roles which have less experience?
- Are there any new roles it might try in the future?

The 21st-century classroom is nowadays full of needs, because they are very different from the 20th-century ones. The 21st century classroom, teachers are students’ facilitators learning and productive creators of classroom environments, which students can develop their skills, they might need at present or in future.

Nevertheless, before as teacher you begin to understand the evolving role of an ESL teacher, let’s outline some of the most popular teacher roles. (Harmer, 2007) talked about the states that ‘it makes more sense to describe different teacher roles and say what they are useful for, rather than make value judgments about their effectiveness.’ So, here you will know some of the most common teacher roles should apply into their classrooms:

Teacher Roles by (Adams, 2010):

Most teachers take on a variety of roles within the classroom, depending on what kind of students and the number of them teachers have; according to that, think about that and select which role do you think most defines you and the kind of role in the ESL classroom are you?

1. *The Controller: 'The teacher is in complete charge of the class, what students do, what they say and how they say it. The teacher assumes this role when a new language is being introduced and accurate reproduction and drilling techniques are needed. In this classroom, the teacher is mostly the centre of focus, the teacher may have the gift of instruction, and can inspire through their knowledge and expertise, but does this role allow for enough student talk time? Is it really enjoyable for the learners? There is also a perception that this role could have a lack of variety in its activities'. (Adams, 2010)*
2. *The Prompter: 'The teacher encourages students to participate and makes suggestions about how students may proceed in an activity. The teacher should be helping students only when necessary. When learners are literally 'lost for words', the prompter can encourage by discreetly nudging students. Students can sometimes lose the thread or become unsure how to proceed; the prompter in this regard can prompt but always in a supportive way'. (Adams, 2010)*
3. *The Resource: 'The teacher is a kind of walking resource centre ready to offer help if needed or provide learners with whatever language they lack when performing communicative activities. The teacher must make her/himself available so that learners can consult her/him when (and only when) it is necessary. As a resource the teacher can guide learners to use available resources such as the internet, for themselves, it certainly isn't necessary to spoon-feed learners, as this might have the downside of making learners reliant on the teacher'. (Adams, 2010)*
4. *The Assessor: 'The teacher assumes this role to see how well students are performing or how well they performed. Feedback and correction are organized and carried out. There are a variety of ways we can grade learners; the role of an assessor allows teachers to correct learners. However, if it is not communicated with sensitivity and support it could prove counter-productive to a student's self-esteem and confidence in learning the target language'. (Adams, 2010)*
5. *The Organizer: 'Perhaps the most difficult and important role the teacher has to play. The success of many activities depends on good organization and on the students knowing*

exactly what they are to do next. Giving instructions is vital in this role as well as setting up activities. The organizer can also serve as a demonstrator, this role also allows a teacher to get involved and engaged with learners. The teacher also serves to open and neatly close activities and also give content feedback'. (Adams, 2010)

6. *The Participant: 'This role improves the atmosphere in the class when the teacher takes part in an activity. However, the teacher takes a risk of dominating the activity when performing it. Here the teacher can enliven a class; if a teacher can stand back and not become the centre of attention, it can be a great way to interact with learners without being too overpowering'. (Adams, 2010)*

7. *The Tutor: 'The teacher acts as a coach when students are involved in project work or self-study. The teacher provides advice and guidance and helps students clarify ideas and limit tasks. This role can be a great way to pay individual attention to a student. It can also allow a teacher to tailor-make a course to fit specific student needs. However, it can also lead to a student becoming too dependent or even too comfortable with one teacher and one method or style of teaching'. (Adams, 2010)*

DISCUSSION

What are the characteristics of The EFL classroom in the 21st century?

When reacting about what students need to be learning today (Armstrong, 2004) assert that an increasingly digital and networked world requires students to be able to demonstrate knowledge, employ information and express ideas compellingly. 201 students need to become not only literate but also able to use that literacy within their information environment in order to succeed now and in the future. The use of that literacy, maintain Armstrong and Warlick, involves, among other things, being able to read deeply for meaning in multimedia content, handle appropriately software tools to process information, use practical and technical skills to communicate knowledge with multimedia, and know the ethical use of the information highway. 201 Students need to become not only literate but also able to use that literacy within their information environment to succeed now and in the future. The use of that literacy, maintain Armstrong and Warlick, involves, among other things, being able to read deeply for meaning in multimedia content, handle appropriate

software tools to process information, use practical and technical skills to communicate knowledge with multimedia, and know the ethical use of the information highway.

In 2001 (Warschauer, 2001), asked a very interesting question, one that is still valid today: What is the role of language teaching in the information technology society? To him, the answer to this question provides English language teaching with new teaching purposes. To begin with, English language educators need to develop activities that engage learners in the kind of authentic tasks and problem-solving activities that they will need in the future. (Warschauer, 2001) suggested that such ‘*engagement can be achieved by having students carry out complex project work involving negotiation, collaboration, goal-setting, meaningful communication, and the development of challenging products*’ (p. 55).

As a result, students need to learn to develop a whole new range of English language literacies, which involve emerging forms of communication, reading, and writing using online technologies. Concretely, War Schauer and armed that English teachers need to use learner-centred collaborative projects, in which students work together with their classmates and with others around the world, using a variety of technological means. Following the proposal of the (New London Group, 1996), he suggested incorporating four basic elements in those projects. See the table below.

Instantly, it had a chance to look at some of the variety of roles, now you let’s see how you as teacher can adopt these into a real classroom activity or task (Adams, 2010):

<i>Activity/Task</i>	<i>How the Teacher Should Behave</i>
<i>Team game</i>	<i>energetic, clear, fair, encouraging</i>
<i>Role Play</i>	<i>supportive, retiring, clear, encouraging</i>
<i>Teacher reading aloud</i>	<i>dramatic, interesting commanding</i>
<i>Whole class listing</i>	<i>efficient, clear, supportive</i>

By: (Adams, 2010)

All we notice here is that the roles are often interchangeable. The role of the teacher is never static. An activity might see an experienced teacher moving gracefully from one character to

another. The 21st-century classroom was designed on the premise that students experience, what they require to enter the 21st-century workplace and live in the global environment. The main characteristics of the 21st-century classroom; consequently, it distinguishes it from the 20th-century classroom. Lectures on only one topic at a time were the norm in the past. Today, collaboration is a thread running through all student learning. Similarly, the collaborative project approach ensures that the curriculum used in this classroom develops two main points:

- *Higher-order thinking skills*
- *Effective communication skills*

Technology skills that students will need for 21st-century careers and the increasingly globalised environment. While there is a place for teacher-centred learning, the evolving ESL teacher must adopt new teaching strategies that are radically different from those employed previously. The curriculum must be more relevant to what students will be exposed to in the 21st century. An interactive teacher is, by definition, one who is fully aware of the group dynamics of a classroom. As (Zoltán Dörnyei, 2003) explained, the success of learning in the classroom depends to a great extent:

- *How students relate to each other and their teacher*
- *What is the atmosphere of the class?*
- *The effectiveness with which students cooperate and communicate with each other*
 - *The roles that not only the teacher plays, but the students participate in*

(Brown, 2000) mentioned “*teachers can play many roles in the course of teaching and this might facilitate learning. Their ability to carry these out effectively will depend to a large extent on the rapport they establish with their students, and of course, on their level of knowledge and skills.*”

According to (Harmer, 2007), ‘*the term ‘facilitator’ is used by many authors to describe a particular kind of teacher, one who is democratic (where the teacher shares some of the leadership with the students) rather than autocratic (where the teacher is in control of*

everything that goes on in the classroom), and one who fosters learner autonomy (where students not only learn on their own but also take responsibility for that learning) through the use of group and pair work and by acting as more of a resource than a transmitter of knowledge'.

Facilitating learning is a way of empowering both student and teacher and relieves the teacher of many of the burdens of being an "expert". Traditionally it would have been seen as a weakness for a teacher to say "I don't know, let's find out" or "I don't know, do any of you students know the answer? But times have changed so must the role of the ELS teacher.

So, it hopes that the next time a teacher teaches a class, consider first how your role might affect your students' learning. Are your classes teacher-centred, with you always at the centre controlling everything, or are you able to "let go" and allow the students to be the centre of attention?

Regardless of the roles, they take on teachers shape the culture of their classes, enhance student learning and influence practice and production. Making the shift from the teacher as an expert to facilitator, sometimes seen as diminishing the power and authority of the teacher, but this should not be the case at all.

How to incorporate 21st century skills into the EFL classroom?

In order to infuse the EFL classroom with 21st-century skills, it believes teachers and students can work with both or either *Multiliteracy and Multimodal Communicative Competence*. According to (Dupuy, 2011), multiliteracy expands the traditional language-based notion of literacy – the ability to read and write – to include not only the ability to produce and interpret texts, but also a critical awareness of the relationships between texts, discourse conventions, and social and cultural contexts. Such ability, asserted Dupuy, prepares learners to participate in diverse discourse communities and fosters the critical engagement they need to design their social futures. In this regard, (Elsner, 2011) maintains that language learners today need to be able to cope with different kinds of texts, including interactive, linear and nonlinear texts, texts with several possible meanings, texts being delivered on paper, screens, or live, and texts that comprise one or more semiotic systems. However, (Haut, 2010) points out that EFL teachers should not only incorporate different types of texts, modes of language and discourses, they should also give explicit instruction

detailing the inherent conventions so that students can learn to move between discourses and become both aware and critical of the intrinsic features that are portrayed.

The process of clarifying and reflecting required a combination of critical and analytical skills as well as the capacity to imagine the kind of [...] teacher they hope to be. In so doing [the teachers] began to construct and articulate a sense of their emerging professional identities ... (p. 5)

(Faulkner & Latham, 2016)

Today, in this 21st century, should know about the skills and abilities that today's students need to succeed in their careers during the Information Age. Find that in the 21st-century, 12 skills need to be shared with our students to succeed in this era:

- *Flexibility*
- *Leadership*
- *Initiative*
- *Productivity*
- *Social skills*
- *Critical thinking*
- *Creativity*
- *Collaboration*
- *Communication*
- *Information literacy*
- *Media literacy*
- *Technology literacy*

These skills are intended to help students keep up with the lightning-pace of today's modern markets. Each skill is unique in how it helps students, but they all have one quality in common.

CONCLUSION

The 21st century English teachers requires the explicit integration of learning and innovation skills, information, media and digital literacy, as well as life and career skills. Therefore, schools in general and primary and secondary classrooms, in particular, should provide

students with practices and processes focused on the acquisition and development of, inter alia, creativity, critical thinking, collaboration, media literacy, initiative and self-direction, and social and intercultural skills. Ultimately, EFL classrooms must be filled with intellectually meaningful and stimulating activities, practices and processes that enable learners not only to effectively articulate thoughts and ideas through oral, written and nonverbal communication, but also to understand complex perspectives, use multiple media and technologies, make judgements and decisions, and work creatively with others. Teachers must therefore critically analyse what the 21st-century movement has to offer in order to enrich their pedagogical processes and instructional practices. Moreover, this analysis can inspire them to innovate to provide their students with opportunities to develop the literacy skills needed in today's world. (Hamilton, 1996) Ultimately, this innovation can not only keep the educational service flexible, responsive and self-renewing but can also promote a sense of well-being in the teaching profession.

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